

»TAP ANYTHING« A DESIGN (CLASS) CASE: TEACHING PARTICIPATORY DESIGN METHODS AS DESIGN BASICS

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ABSTRACT

This report looks at a higher education design class as a design case for teaching participatory design methods to beginning design students from different design disciplines (communication, product, and interface design). The class was an experiment in so far as basic design education usually focuses on other elementary aspects first, such as form, color, representation, etc. The experiment's purpose was to confront design students very early on in the program with a participatory design approach and find out how well they can handle and apply it and how valuable it is for their basic design education. The report describes the overall aim, structure, process, and outcomes of the design class at University of Applied Sciences Potsdam and takes a peep into the near future.

KEYWORDS: *design methods, co-design, teaching design, education, prototyping*

INTRODUCTION

During the winter semester of 2013/14, from October to February, a design class at University of Applied Sciences Potsdam (FHP) took place that explored teaching participatory design methods and approaches to first and second year design students. The aim of the class was twofold: firstly, it was all about learning and applying design methods, mainly the participatory design method but also related methods from user-centered design such as ethnography, probes, usability testing, etc. We pretty much undertook a 'journey' through Liz Sander's 'Topography of Design Research' (2006, fig. 1). Whereas later on in design education it is important to choose the design method well and wisely, and the student should be able to explain why he or she used this particular method, in the design basics approach described in this report the aim was to get in touch with different methods in a light and playful way, to get to know them and have them on ones skill-palette for future design projects.

The class was project-oriented, so along with the participatory design approach there was also a specific subject matter: the class was named 'Alles mal antatschen', German for 'tap anything', after a rather cynical article about interactive

children's books (Wellershoff 2013). We explored the use of the Smartboard, or Digital Whiteboard (e.g. Mimio 2014), and its possibilities in the classroom from a design perspective, as classrooms are massively upgraded with this technology today. Teachers though often lack time, ideas and knowledge to deploy it fruitfully and creatively in class. For example, in an interview we learned that one math teacher spent a whole summer designing an interactive application for the Smartboard. Surely designers can help here!

DESIGN BRIEF

The task for the design students was to design an interactive learning or reading application for the Smartboard to be used in a primary school class. Target group: primary school kids, 1–4 years old. Implementation: prototype with interactive features to run on the actual Smartboard in the primary school classroom. Method: deploying a participatory design process (Sanders 2004, 2013), getting in touch and in conversation with future users and target groups (pupils and teachers), doing 'fieldwork', doing user-centered design.

DESIGN PROCESS

Thus, the students design process was structured in nine main consecutive and interacting steps:

1. Expert input
2. Preliminary interviews
3. Observation
4. Ideas and prototypes
5. Testing
6. Participatory workshop
7. Iteration
8. Presentation
9. Feedback

Below the process from step 1 to 7 is visualized as a flow chart (fig. 1) and mapped onto Sander's 'Topology of Design Research' (fig.2).

From design question through several steps in the design process to the design answer/outcome

Expert Input

To start off we got an introduction to teaching with Smartboards and to the technology in general from our partner school (Grundschule im Bornstedter Feld 2013) and a company who releases digital animated primers for a mutual reading experience in the classroom (Onilo, 2013).

Figure 1. Structure and Process of the Design Class.

Preliminary Interviews

Students conducted interviews with teachers and/or pupils among their acquaintances with a participatory/ideation element in the form of a design probe (Gaver et al 1999, see fig. 4).

Observation

To learn through the method of observing, students sat in classes and watched the application of Smartboards carefully. We undertook the observation in a different school in Berlin (Rixdorfer Schule 2013) to experience a different demographic (more pupils with migration backgrounds, less financially strong families compared to the school in Potsdam).

Figure 2. Topography of Design Research after Sanders (2006), numbers show the according step in our design process.

Figure 4. Design Probes Used in the Interviews: 'draw what you would like to see on a magic board in the classroom'.

Figure 5. Observing the Use of the Smartboard and Other Details in the Classroom.

Figure 6. Lo-fi Testing of the Prototypes with Paper Prototyping and Click-through on Laptops and TVs.

Ideas and Prototypes

Based on expert input, interviews and observation in the field, first ideas, concepts, and designs for interactive Smartboard learning applications emerged. To be able to go into further discussions with the target group prototypes were necessary. Since there were several first-year students in the group, the method to implement the prototypes had to be simple and quick to learn. We chose to use Apple's Keynote application for quick building of interactive prototypes (e.g. Keynotopia 2013) as it requires very little previous knowledge and students today are already familiar with presentation software like Keynote or PowerPoint from presentations they are making in high school classes. The results were highly useful 'clickable' prototypes we could use for the next phase.

Testing

Over the Christmas holidays, about halfway through the semester, students had to conduct a private usability test with

their prototypes with friends and family at home. Like in a classic usability test they tested design, understanding, interaction and interface design and also retrieved open comments and ideas for their concepts and prototypes. The test settings varied: as we could not test on the actual classroom, Smartboard students used their laptops, TVs, occasionally projections, as well as paper prototypes to walk children through their ideas. The outcome was analyzed and put into writing for further utilization.

Participatory Workshop

Preparation: Parallel to the testing a big workshop on site in the school was organized and prepared. Preparing the workshop was an essential part of the class. The aim was to convey that the preparation was as much an act of designing as designing the prototypes, the actual design product. Students developed themselves a concept for the workshop and produced very creative tools and guidelines to run the workshop (see fig. 7).

Figure 7. Tools, Questionnaires and Guidelines for the Workshop.

Figure 8. 'Testing-Groups: Kids Trying Out the Prototypes, Effective and Funny Rating System Using Cardboard Plates with Smiley Faces.

Figure 9. 'Ideation-Groups: Augmenting Paper Prototypes with Features, Drawing Fantasy Smartboards and Game Playing.

Workshop: The workshop took place one afternoon in early January 2014, from 2:00 to 4:00 p.m. The participants were 40 school-kids (ages 1-4 and 6-11), 3 teachers, 21 workshop organizers (19 university students, 2 university teachers). The kids were divided into four groups and there was one additional teacher group. Each group was accompanied by 3-4 design students.

Group 1 and 2: Testing

Groups showed prototypes on the Smartboard in the classroom and talked about them with the kids. The kids were the 'jury' and were asked to rate certain aspects (legibility, color, fun, etc.) with a special rating system. Kids could also come to the boards, interact with the prototypes, and make comments (see fig. 8).

Group 3 and 4: Ideation

Groups played games to learn about the children's interests and let them draw on 'magic Smartboards' or add fantasy features to their existing prototypes (see fig. 9). The groups were very colorful, noisy, creatively messy, and merry.

Group 5: Teacher focus group

There was a round-table discussion and brainstorming with teachers about several topics that came up in the design process, such as: what were the obstacles while using the Smartboards, what worked, what did not, was the technical and infrastructure supportive so that they could build applications themselves, what could be improved, etc.

Each group had a session of 20 minutes and then alternated rooms, so every group was in every room once (except the teacher group).

Iteration

Findings, inspirations, and new ideas from the workshop were again analyzed, put into writing and then together with the private testing results used for an iteration of the existing prototypes. The changes that were made to the prototypes varied. Some only changed details, colors, illustration styles, etc.; others changed their concept much more profoundly, and some even completely discarded their concept and developed a new one.

PRESENTATION AND FEEDBACK

Three weeks after the workshop took place we held a final presentation at the school with the revised concepts and design. Attendees were several teachers, the head of school, some school-kids as well as colleagues and researchers from the university. All students showed their working interactive prototypes on the Smartboard. Each student presented his or her concept in four minutes sharp, followed by a two-minute open feedback round. As this was the very first public presentation for most of the class, this was also a great training for them. The feedback during the presentation was very constructive, positive and interesting. Feedback from the teachers was specially valuable for future developments and projects.

The very important last step in the design-class process and in the semester was the internal feedback round in class between the university teacher, the co-teacher, and the students. Here, the whole process and all the methods and steps were analyzed and the future use of those methods and value for the design process discussed.

DISCUSSION

The process throughout the semester was highly motivated and concentrated, and the outcomes very rich. It was a great pleasure to teach this class.

The group was diverse: not only was it a mixed student-group from different design disciplines (communication, product, and interface design), but their level of experience varied. For some of the students it was their first semester, and therefore their very first contact with design after high school. Some were in their second year of study and already had an idea of the design profession, others were going through an apprenticeship and were learning a related technical profession. The feedback from all those students (and also from the school) was throughout very positive. It was a novel approach to design for all of them, experienced or inexperienced. With respect to participatory design they were all beginners and therefore worked together beautifully. The class was evaluated via an anonymous questionnaire (17 participants) and an oral feedback round. Most students said the methods they learned were very valuable tools and they planned to keep using them in their further studies. Particularly, the testing was often mentioned as highly enlightening. Also the 'field-work' aspect – working with the 'real world' – was pointed out to be very inspiring, motivating and eye-opening.

More analysis is required to fully assess this class in terms of teaching methods to be able to build upon the lessons learned for future course development. The experiment to make a participatory 'fieldwork'-like design approach the subject-matter of a design basics class was very promising; it will be interesting and important though to observe the development of the participating design students to learn if taking this class will have an impact on their approach and understanding of the role of design in their future projects.

We look forward to future collaborations with the primary school and hope that some prototypes will turn into major design projects in the following semesters. After all, public education could be a huge and interesting field for designers, where design skills are greatly needed and very welcome. Sadly, due to the lack of public funds for the educational sector, this area is not yet of great interest to design firms and the like. However, as long as this is the case, we can always think of Victor Papanek and his invitation to designers to dedicate 10% of their working time and energy to non-profit social projects (Papanek 1971). Forty years later this is still a valid concept.

Figure 10. Final Presentation and Feedback Round in School-Classroom at 'Grundschule im Bornstedter Feld'.

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